

The Drakenstein Trust

Introduction

- The number of propagules, position in the landscape and cultivation effort surrounding the introduction of a non-indigenous tree species is dictated by the human use driving the introduction event (Fig 1).
- These conditions will affect the chance of a species “escaping” and becoming a successful invasive (Fig 1).
- Thus, species introduced for the same human use will have commonalities in the way they have spread into the new landscape and ultimately similarities in their invasive distributions .
- Australian *Acacia* were introduced for three main human uses, dune stabilization, forestry and as ornamental plants in gardens .
- The aim of this work is to investigate the relationship between human use and the invasive spread and distribution of invasive *Acacia* in South Africa.

Methods

- Three SDM’s calibrated with different distribution data (AUN) Native Australian distribution data (i.e. native realized niche), (RSA) RSA distribution data (i.e. global records combined (i.e. as close to the fundamental niche as possible) were generated for each of the 11 selected *Acacia* species in South Africa.

Hypothesis 1

Climate similarity between AUN and RSA distributions of “uninformed” ornamental species will be weaker than forestry and dune stabilization species planted in “informed”, matched climates (Fig 2).

- RSA and AUN model predictions were compared using ENMTools (Warren et al. 2010) to calculate the Schoener (1968) D index and the Hellinger-based similarity statistic (I) (Van der Vaart 1998) for each grid cell. Both measures give a value between 0 (no overlap) and 1 (complete overlap).

Hypothesis 2

Forestry and dune stabilization species will have been exposed to a greater proportion of the fundamental niche in their invasive range than ornamental species and thus match it’s climatic conditions more closely.

- RSA and GLO model predictions were compared for each species to assess how much of the fundamental niche had been occupied by the invasive population.

Results

- The overlap between RSA and AUN models were consistently lower for species introduced as ornamentals than species introduced for forestry and dune stabilization (**Table 1**).
- The overlap between RSA and GLO models was fairly consistent across all the species, with the *Acacia longifolia* and *Acacia mearnsii* having least and greatest similarity between the two climate based niches respectively (**Table 1**).

Table 1. D-values of comparisons of projections of models calibrated with native distribution data and invasive distribution data for 11 invasive Australian *Acacia* species (0=no overlap, 1= complete overlap) .

Reason for introduction	Species	Overlap (D) /Similarity(I)	
		Hyp1: RSA–AUN	Hyp2: RSA–GLO
Uninformed (ornamental, n=3)	<i>A. baileyana</i>	0.00 / 0.00	0.54 / 0.75
	<i>A. elata</i>	0.19 / 0.32	0.61 / 0.81
	<i>A. podalyriifolia</i>	0.23 / 0.44	0.62 / 0.78
Informed (forestry, n=4)	<i>A. dealbata</i>	0.45 / 0.71	0.48 / 0.68
	<i>A. decurrens</i>	0.52 / 0.72	0.55 / 0.75
	<i>A. mearnsii</i>	0.50 / 0.72	0.76 / 0.91
	<i>A. melanoxylon</i>	0.43 / 0.66	0.44 / 0.67
Informed (dune stabilization, n=4)	<i>A. cyclops</i>	0.43 / 0.59	0.71 / 0.86
	<i>A. longifolia</i>	0.38 / 0.58	0.36 / 0.58
	<i>A. pycnantha</i>	0.48 / 0.70	0.52 / 0.72
	<i>A. saligna</i>	0.47 / 0.67	0.57 / 0.81

Figure 1. Populations of the ornamental *Acacia elata* (A and B) , forestry plantations of *Acacia mearnsii* (C and D) and dune stabilizing *Acacia saligna* (E and F) in South Africa. Yellow represents deliberate plantings, while red represents plants that have escaped cultivation and are invading the surrounding habitat.

Figure 2. Suitability maps of South Africa calibrated with Australian distribution points for the dune stabilization species *A. saligna* (A) and ornamental *A. elata* (B). Black triangles represent main areas where initial introductions occurred).

Discussion

- Species introduced randomly into the landscape as ornamentals trees occupy climatic niches that have little or no overlap with their native realized niche space. This could prove problematic when trying to predict where ornamental species are likely to invade using native range distribution data.
- Contrary to predictions, the exposure of species to environments that could suit their spread appears to be similar at the national scale.
- The inability to predict areas susceptible to invasion, combined with the wide exposure of ornamental plants to areas that appear climatically suitable for spread is particularly concerning when the growing number of trees species involved in the ornamental trade and the difficulties surrounding the management of ornamental plant movement is considered.

Conclusion

- Human use has a clear influence on the way a species is introduced to a novel landscape, which in turn has an impact on the invasive distribution of the relevant species. Thus, management attempting to limit future invasions need to take into account the reason behind an introduction event when using information from their native range to analyze the invasive risk of a species.